

13

Abstract

14 In the present paper, we explore the temporal dynamics of the flanker effect in the tactile
15 modality and compare it with findings in the visual modality. We created a tactile version of
16 the flanker task in which we presented groups of dots oriented either vertically or
17 horizontally to participant's fingertips. The target stimulus was presented to the middle
18 finger, while the flanker stimuli were presented to the index and the ring fingers.
19 Distributional analyses of the latency data show a tactile flanker effect: an overall facilitation
20 for congruent target-flanker trials relative to incongruent trials, and a higher effect size for
21 slower correct responses (higher quantiles) than for faster correct responses (lower quantiles).
22 While this congruency effect may resemble the one typically reported in the visual modality,
23 there are differences between these two modalities as well, mainly related to the relative
24 speed of error and correct responses. These differences suggest that some of the mechanisms
25 responsible for the flanker effect differ across sensory modalities.

26

Keywords: Eriksen flanker, tactile attention, touch

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Word count: 5071

The Tactile Eriksen Flanker Effect: A Time Course Analysis

In our daily life, we are exposed to large amounts of complex stimulation through our senses. To successfully navigate the world, we select the relevant information and disregard the potentially irrelevant information from our environment. Notably, our perception not only depends on the information we selectively attend to, but also upon the context that surrounds it. *Context effects* (also called congruency effects, or interference effects) demonstrate the influence of irrelevant contextual information on our perception of the attended stimuli. In laboratory settings, these effects are commonly evidenced in tasks in which participants are asked to respond to target stimulus while ignoring distracting stimuli irrelevant to the task, known as conflict paradigms.

While most research on the influence of distractors on the perception of the target has been conducted in the visual and auditory modalities (see Driver, 2001, for a review), the interest on the sense of touch has significantly grown during the last two decades (see Gallace & Spence, 2014). The study of tactile selective attention is important for both applied and theoretical reasons. Understanding how we perceive and recognize tactile information, as well as the circumstances that facilitate or hinder such perception, is needed for the development and optimization of devices that give tactile feedback; for example, those providing tactile warning signals to drivers (see Meng & Spence, 2015). In addition, determining which aspects of the processing of attended stimuli are modality-independent and which are modality-dependent (e.g., Katus & Eimer, 2018; Murphy, Dalton, & Spence, 2017) is crucial for theory development.

In this paper, we examined how tactile contextual irrelevant information affects the discrimination of attended stimuli. To do so, we created a tactile version of a well-known conflict paradigm, the Eriksen flanker task, in which we asked participants to indicate whether the pattern of dots presented to the middle finger of their dominant hand was horizontally oriented (i.e., ••) or vertically oriented (i.e., $\begin{smallmatrix} \bullet \\ \bullet \\ \bullet \end{smallmatrix}$) while ignoring the distractors

54 presented simultaneously in the index and ring fingers of the same hand. Such distractors
55 were either congruent or incongruent with the target. We analyzed how attended and
56 unattended stimuli are processed as a function of time, and compared our data with results
57 found in the visual modality with the aim of exploring the similarities and differences
58 between the time course of tactile and visual flanker effects.

59 Before diving into the details of our study, we first describe conflict paradigms and
60 briefly review previous experiments on the processing of unattended stimuli in non-visual
61 settings.

62 **Conflict tasks**

63 Conflict tasks present stimuli that have both task-relevant and task-irrelevant features.
64 One of the most common conflict paradigms is the Eriksen flanker task (Eriksen & Eriksen,
65 1974), which was initially designed for the visual modality (see Stroop, 1935; or Simon, 1969,
66 for other conflict tasks). In the flanker task, participants perform a classification of a target
67 stimulus that is flanked by either congruent non-target stimuli (i.e., linked to the same
68 response as the target), or incongruent non-target stimuli (i.e., linked to the opposite
69 response as the target). Therefore, for this task, the relevant information is the identity of
70 the target, whereas the irrelevant information is the identity of the stimuli that surrounds it.
71 Critically, the classification of the target is more difficult when the flanking stimuli are
72 incongruent than when they are congruent with the target, as shown by longer reaction times
73 (RTs) and lower accuracy in the incongruent condition than in the congruent condition.

74 The flanker effect has been reported mainly in the visual modality. However,
75 flanker-like effects have also been shown with tactile stimulation. For example, Evans and
76 Craig (1991) asked subjects to identify the direction in which a pattern of vibrating dots
77 moved across one fingertip while ignoring the pattern of vibrating dots presented to an
78 adjacent fingertip, which could move in the same or opposite direction (i.e., congruent

79 vs. incongruent conditions). To present the stimuli, the authors used two 6×24
80 electromechanical tactile matrices of dots (one per fingerpad). Those dot grids were a
81 component of a technology no longer manufactured (i.e., Optacon; (Linvill & Bliss, 1966)).
82 To create the movement sensation, different arrays of dots were activated in either a
83 row-by-row or a column-by-column manner to create the vertical or horizontal movement,
84 respectively. They reported slower and less accurate responses when non-targets were
85 incongruent than when they were congruent with the target. In a subsequent study using the
86 same apparatus, Evans, Craig, and Rinker (1992) found the same effect when the non-target
87 stimulus was presented to non-adjacent fingers of the same hand, when presented across
88 hands even when increasing the distance between them, and when the vibratory dots were
89 stationary (i.e., only one row of dots was activated), and participants were asked to make a
90 judgement about the location of the vibration.

91 Similarly, Driver and Grossenbacher (1996) presented participants with either one or
92 two vibratory pulses simultaneously in both hands and were asked to report the number of
93 pulses in one hand while ignoring the other; they found a congruency effect that,
94 interestingly, decreased as the distance between the hands increased (see also Soto-Faraco,
95 Ronald, & Spence, 2004). The dissimilarity in results regarding the influence of distance on
96 the congruency effect size has been attributed to differences in methodology because the
97 maximum hand distance, the task instructions, and the nature of the stimuli were different
98 across studies (see Soto-Faraco et al., 2004). Regardless of the specific mechanism in play,
99 these experiments suggest that unattended tactile stimuli affect the processing of the
100 attended stimuli. Moreover, although these studies are not set up as a classic flanker task,
101 because the target was not surrounded by irrelevant information, they suggest that
102 flanker-like effects can appear in the tactile modality. Notably, single distractor setups are
103 not uncommon in the visual modality (e.g., Stuart, McAnally, & Meehan, 2003).

104 However, in spite of the results shown by the studies described above, there would be
105 two reasons to doubt that a flanker effect exists in the tactile modality. The first one is that

106 for most tactile stimuli, we do not have an automatized classificaton; keep in mind that in
107 the visual flanker task common symbols such as “<” or letters are often used. The other
108 reason is that there is some existing literature on lack of effects in the tactile modality that
109 are extremely robust in the visual modality like the trasnposed-letter effect (Perea,
110 Garcia-Chamorro, Martin-Suesta, & Gomez, 2012). Hence, the first question in this research
111 was if there is indeed a tactile flanker effect; cutting to the chase, yes, there is a flanker effect.

112 In addition, none of the previous studies have examined the time course of the conflict.
113 Time course analyses are crucial to understand the mechanisms underlying an effect. Indeed,
114 in the visual modality, fine-grained analyses that go beyond average-level comparisons have
115 revealed that the flanker effect is not constant over time (e.g., Gratton, Coles, & Donchin,
116 1992). The time course of a tactile effect might help us discriminate between different
117 hypotheses on the trajectory of the conflict - ideas discussed in the following paragraphs.
118 Thus, the second question in the present paper was whether the time-course of the tactile
119 flanker effect resembled the time-course of the visual flanker effect shown in the literature.

120 **Beyond mean RTs**

121 While comparing the performance across conditions using mean RTs is an appropriate
122 method to establish the presence of an effect, central tendency measurements are somewhat
123 coarse if the goal is to uncover the temporal dynamics of cognitive function. Time course
124 analyses are very useful in examining the mechanisms that underlie cognitive phenomena.
125 Indeed, such analyses have revealed differences among seemingly equivalent conflict tasks in
126 the visual modality (e.g., Pratte, Rouder, Morey, & Feng, 2010), and these results have led
127 to new, more sophisticated versions of visual selective attention tasks (e.g., Burle, Spieser,
128 Servant, & Hasbroucq, 2014; Hübner & Töbel, 2019). In this paper we use, in addition to
129 mean RT and mean accuracy, three methods to explore the time course of the tactile flanker
130 effects: delta plots, quantile probability functions, and conditional accuracy functions (see
131 Figure 1 for an example).

132 *Delta plots* are residual quantile plots. They display, on the y-axis, the RT difference
133 for correct responses between two conditions and, on the x-axis, the mean RT for a specific
134 quantile. Thus, they offer a visual representation of the effect size over time. In the visual
135 flanker task, delta plots have a positive slope, showing an increase of the flanker effect as RT
136 increases (e.g., Gratton et al., 1992; Hübner & Töbel, 2019).

137 *Quantile Probability Functions (QPFs)* provide a rich summary of the whole dataset.
138 For each condition, they show the probabilities of correct and error responses as well as the
139 RT distributions for correct and error responses. A point in the y-axis indicates the mean
140 RT at a specific quantile (.1, .3, .5, .7, and .9, from lowest to highest), and a column on the
141 x-axis indicates the probability of a response for a specific condition, with correct responses
142 on the right and errors on the left. This way, one can compare the relative speed of error and
143 correct responses for each condition. In the visual flanker task, QPFs show that 1) the
144 proportion of correct responses is higher for congruent trials than for incongruent trials; 2)
145 for incongruent trials, error responses are faster than correct responses, and 3) correct
146 responses to incongruent trials are slower than correct responses to congruent trials, (e.g.,
147 White, Ratcliff, & Starns, 2011).

148 *Conditional Accuracy Function (CAF)* display the relationship between accuracy and
149 RT for each condition. In the visual flanker task, CAFs have revealed that accuracy for
150 congruent trials is high and constant across RT quantiles, but for incongruent trials is
151 relatively low for fast responses and increases as RT increases, approaching the level of the
152 congruent condition for slow responses (e.g., Gratton, Coles, Sirevaag, Eriksen, & Donchin,
153 1988; Hübner & Töbel, 2019; Stins, Polderman, Boomsma, & Geus, 2007).

154 -Please insert Figure 1 around here -

155 The three exploratory data analysis methods described above, together with measures
156 of central tendency, allow us to examine whether a tactile flanker effect emerges when two
157 distractors surround the target, as well as the way our dependent variables (i.e., RT and

158 accuracy) are influenced by the congruency of the flankers. Particularly, we can assess when
159 in the trial distractors generate more error responses, and the costs associated with
160 incongruent distractors for correct responses. In the visual modality, information about the
161 time course of the flanker effect has been used to create theories and models that explain the
162 processing underlying performance in the flanker task. These theories generally assume that
163 attention is a dynamic process, suggesting that visual selectivity increases over time (e.g.,
164 Eriksen & Schultz, 1979, Eriksen & James, 1986; Heitz & Engle, 2007, for continuous
165 selectivity accounts; and Hübner, Steinhauser, & Lehle, 2010; Ridderinkhof, 1997, for discrete
166 selectivity accounts). Here, we explore whether this is the case in the tactile modality.

167 Given our focus on distributional features and the time course of the effects on the
168 data, we believe it is *useful* (Box, 1976) to think about the flanker task in terms of evidence
169 accumulation models. While there are many versions of such models, they all share a
170 common assumption: sensory stimulation is encoded into tokens of information that are
171 accumulated until a decision criterion is reached. In many implementations, this
172 accumulation of evidence is stochastic (meaning that it has an average rate, but also a
173 variability). The advantage of this line of thought is that there is a robust tradition of
174 evidence accumulation modeling in the visual modality (e.g., Brown & Heathcote, 2008;
175 Ratcliff, 1978; Stone, 1960). Indeed, models that explain how the congruency effects are
176 generated in the flanker task in the visual modality have also been implemented within this
177 framework (see Hübner & Töbel, 2012; Ulrich, Schröter, Leuthold, & Birngruber, 2015;
178 White, Brown, & Ratcliff, 2012; White et al., 2011); hence, the third and final question in
179 this paper is if the time course data can be explained within evidence accumulation models.

180 We find thinking about the tactile flanker task in terms of evidence accumulation
181 modeling useful because we can implement different hypotheses of the tactile flanker effect.
182 Specifically, we can think of three possible hypotheses of the tactile flanker effect that
183 correspond to implementations of the evidence accumulation model (a process model) that,
184 in turn, correspond to a statistical model (i.e., a model of the data): (1) Hypothesis₀: there

Method

211

212 Participants

213 Thirty-three students from DePaul University participated for course-credit in an
 214 introductory psychology course. Also, the three authors participated in this study. None of
 215 the participants were braille readers.

216 Apparatus

217 A refreshable braille display was used to present stimuli (Focus 40 Blue, Freedom
 218 Scientific). The display was placed in the pull-out keyboard tray of a desk to avoid
 219 participants seeing it, while the keyboard used to make the responses was placed on top of
 220 the desk. To present stimuli on the braille display and record participant's responses we
 221 created a shell script using bash syntax that displays the stimuli in the computer's terminal
 222 and utilized the OS-X's VoiceOver accessibility feature to present the items in the terminal
 223 on the braille display¹.

224 Material

225 We used two braille characters as stimuli: braille pattern dots-123 (⠠), and pattern
 226 dots-25 (⠠); from now on we refer to them as the vertical and the horizontal stimulus,
 227 respectively. These characters were combined in arrays of three, where the first and last (the
 228 flankers) always matched and were either congruent or incongruent with the character in the
 229 middle (the target). As can be seen in Figure 3, congruent stimuli were ⠠ ⠠ ⠠
 230 and ⠠ ⠠ ⠠, and incongruent stimuli were ⠠ ⠠ ⠠ and ⠠ ⠠ ⠠.
 231 These stimuli were presented on the refreshable braille display. Each participant perceived
 232 168 trials, 50% congruent, presented in random order.

¹ The online repository, available at <https://osf.io/89p3c/>, provides the bash code and the stimuli lists we utilized to carry out this experiment along with the data collected, data analyses, and data wrangling scripts.

233 Procedure

234 We asked participants to place their index, middle, and ring fingers of their dominant
235 hand on three specific braille cells separated 1.8 cm (there was an empty cell in the braille
236 display between each of the used cells; see Figure 3). Participants were told that a pattern of
237 dots would appear underneath each of those fingertips. We asked them to report as fast and
238 as accurately as possible, whether the pattern presented to the middle finger was a vertical
239 or a horizontal line of dots. They did so by pressing the keys labeled “|” or “-” , with their
240 non-dominant hand, while ignoring the patterns presented on the other fingertips. Both the
241 target and the flanker stimuli were presented on the braille display until a response was
242 made, and the inter-trial interval (ITI) was one second. RTs and accuracy were recorded in
243 each trial. The experimental session lasted approximately fifteen minutes.

244 -Please insert Figure 3 around here -

245 Results

246 Mean RTs and accuracy

247 The data files and scripts for data wrangling and analyses are available at
248 <https://osf.io/89p3c/>. Participants who performed below 55% ($n = 3$), and trials in which
249 responses were either faster than 100 ms or slower than 2000 ms were excluded from the
250 analysis. Overall, 5271 trials were analyzed (6048 – trials from low accuracy participants –
251 timeouts). Because we used braille cells (i.e., horizontal lines •• use two dots and vertical
252 lines ⋮ use three dots), the horizontal and vertical stimuli used in the experiment were
253 different in their structure, which could influence their perceptual identifiability and
254 discriminability.² We analyzed accuracy and RTs by congruency condition (i.e., congruent

² We thank an anonymous reviewer for noticing this difference between the horizontal and vertical stimuli, and for suggesting these analyses.

255 vs. incongruent) and by target type (i.e., horizontal vs. vertical). Table 1 shows the means
256 for accuracy, and RTs for correct and error responses for each of those variables.

257 -Please insert Table 1 around here -

258 For RTs, we analyzed the data of correct responses using a linear mixed effects model
259 (lmer function: lme4 and lmerTest packages in R; Bates, Mächler, Bolker, & Walker, 2015;
260 and Kuznetsova, Brockhoff, & Christensen, 2017, respectively) with Congruency Condition
261 and Target Type as fixed factors and Subject as random factor (see Appendix for the code
262 and complete output). Results evidenced main effects of Congruency ($B = -0.065$,
263 $SE = 0.007$, $t = -8.940$, $p < 0.001$) and Target Type ($B = -0.06$, $SE = 0.007$, $t = -8.165$,
264 $p < 0.001$), as well as an interaction between them ($B = 0.07$, $SE = 0.015$, $t = 4.752$,
265 $p < 0.001$). To further analyze whether the congruency effect exists for both types of stimuli,
266 we analyzed separately horizontal and vertical stimuli using the same model described above.
267 Results revealed a congruency effect for both horizontal ($t(32) = -9.563$, $p < 0.001$, d
268 $= .357$) and vertical ($t(32) = -3.219$, $p = 0.001$, $d = .112$) target types, larger for the former.³

269 For accuracy, we analyzed the data using a generalized linear mixed effects model
270 (glmer function: lme4 package in R; Bates et al., 2015), again with Congruency Condition
271 and Target Type as fixed factors and Subject as random factor. Results revealed main effects
272 of Congruency ($B = 1.486$, $SE = 0.097$, $z = 15.310$, $p < 0.001$, $d = 1.641$) and target type
273 ($B = 0.484$, $SE = 0.096$, $z = 5.015$, $p < 0.001$, $d = .534$), but there were no signs of an
274 interaction between the two factors ($B = 0.144$, $SE = 0.193$, $z = 0.746$, $p = 0.456$).

275 Therefore, the task used in the present experiment produced a substantial flanker
276 effect: responses to congruent trials were more accurate and faster than to incongruent trials.

³ We calculated effect sizes for mixed-effects models following Brysbaert and Stevens (2018) suggestions, taking into account the random effects. In these models, effects sizes are smaller than those obtained in t-tests or ANOVAS (e.g., a big effect size in an ANOVA [i.e., $>.8$] may become less than 0.1 when using mixed-effects models; see Brysbaert & Stevens, 2018 for discussion)

277 This effect is present in horizontal and vertical target stimuli. However, for horizontal
278 stimuli, responses were slower and the congruency effect larger than for vertical stimuli. This
279 indicates the horizontal target (••) was more difficult to recognize than the vertical target
280 (••); (see Figure 4).

281 -Please insert Figure 4 around here -

282 **Time-course analyses**

283 For the analysis of the effect size over time, we used the delta plot technique. This is a
284 quantile by quantile residual plot that displays distributional differences across conditions
285 (De Jong, Liang, & Lauber, 1994). RTs per condition and participant at the .1, .3, .5, .7, and
286 .9 quantiles were calculated, then, the difference between conditions for every quantile was
287 computed per subject and averaged across subjects (see Figure 5). The delta plot describing
288 the mean effect size across quantiles has a positive slope and an intercept above zero. In
289 other words, the flanker effect is present across all quantiles and increases for higher
290 quantiles (slower responses). We submitted the data per participant to a linear mixed effects
291 model (lme4 package in R; Bates et al., 2015) with linear and quadratic fixed effects, $\text{delta} \sim$
292 $\text{mean RT} + I(\text{meanRT})^2 + (1|\text{Subject})$, showing evidence of a positive slope (linear
293 component: $B = 0.317$, $SE = 0.155$, $t = 2.05$, $p < 0.05$, quadratic component:
294 $B = -7.957^{-5}$, $SE = 6.988^{-5}$, $t = -1.139$, $p = 0.257$). Indeed, a likelihood ratio test
295 between linear and linear-quadratic models showed that adding the quadratic component
296 does not improve model fit (see Table 2).

297 -Please insert Figure 5 here -

298 -Please insert Table 2 around here -

299 For the analysis of the accuracy data over time, we used quantile probability functions
300 (QPFs) and conditional accuracy functions (CAFs). As explained earlier, the QPFs inform
301 about the distributions of response times for correct and error responses per condition (i.e.,
302 RT distributions for error-congruent, error-incongruent, correct-incongruent, and
303 correct-congruent). The CAFs reveal how accuracy per condition changes as a function of
304 time (i.e., mean accuracy per RT quantile for congruent and for incongruent trials).

305 To create the QPF, we calculated the proportion of errors and correct responses for the
306 congruent and the incongruent trials and averaged them across participants. Then, for each
307 response (i.e., error and correct responses to congruent trials, and error and correct responses
308 to incongruent trials), we computed the mean RTs at the .1, .3, .5, .7, and .9 quantiles and
309 average them across subjects (these averaged quantiles are also known as Vincentiles).
310 Because there were few error responses to congruent trials, only the median for that
311 condition was calculated (see White et al., 2011). Thus, each column provides a summary of
312 the distribution of RT for errors and correct responses per condition. The QPF plot can be
313 seen in Figure 6. It shows the typical flanker effect: for correct responses (the two columns
314 on the right-hand end of the x-axis), congruent trials yielded more accurate and faster
315 responses than the incongruent trials, as statistically evidenced by the linear mixed effects
316 models. Moreover, the difference in response times between congruent and incongruent trials
317 increases slightly as responses get slower (i.e., higher quantiles), as was also shown in the
318 delta plot. Interestingly, for incongruent trials (white squares) error responses were not faster
319 than correct responses to incongruent trials, unlike findings in the visual modality (see,
320 White et al., 2011). QPFs are visual exploratory data analysis methods (Tukey, 1977) for
321 which there are no established inferential statistical analyses. Nonetheless, they are a great
322 tool to visualize data, providing a big picture of the relationships between conditions.

323 -Please insert Figure 6 around here -

324 To create the conditional accuracy functions (CAFs), we calculated the mean accuracy

325 per condition within the five time-bands with an equal number of responses (i.e., .1, .3, .5, .7,
 326 and .9 quantiles). As can be seen in Figure 7, accuracy for the congruent condition was
 327 higher than for the incongruent condition across all RT quantiles and this difference is
 328 approximately constant over time. Indeed, a bayesian analysis of variance⁴ showed a lack of
 329 an interaction between Condition and Quantile when explaining accuracy ($BF_{10} = 0.001$).
 330 This CAF differs from those found in the visual flanker task, where accuracy for incongruent
 331 trials is below chance for the first quantile and increases for slower responses up to the
 332 accuracy level of incongruent trials (e.g., Gratton et al., 1988).

333 -Please insert Figure 7 around here -

334 Discussion

335 We created a tactile flanker task to examine the flanker congruency effect in the tactile
 336 modality when presenting two distractors surrounding the target, and to explore the
 337 temporal dynamics of the responses. To do so, we asked participants to focus their attention
 338 on the middle finger of their dominant hand, where we presented the target braille pattern
 339 (either $\bullet\bullet$ or $\begin{smallmatrix} \bullet \\ \bullet \\ \bullet \end{smallmatrix}$), and, simultaneously, two distractors were presented to the adjacent ring
 340 and index fingers, which could be congruent (i.e., $\bullet\bullet \quad \bullet\bullet \quad \bullet\bullet$ or $\begin{smallmatrix} \bullet \\ \bullet \\ \bullet \end{smallmatrix} \quad \begin{smallmatrix} \bullet \\ \bullet \\ \bullet \end{smallmatrix} \quad \begin{smallmatrix} \bullet \\ \bullet \\ \bullet \end{smallmatrix}$) or
 341 incongruent (i.e., $\bullet\bullet \quad \begin{smallmatrix} \bullet \\ \bullet \\ \bullet \end{smallmatrix} \quad \bullet\bullet$ or $\begin{smallmatrix} \bullet \\ \bullet \\ \bullet \end{smallmatrix} \quad \bullet\bullet \quad \begin{smallmatrix} \bullet \\ \bullet \\ \bullet \end{smallmatrix}$) with the target. Participants had to
 342 identify the target by pressing one of the two response keys (i.e., “|” or “-”).

343 Results showed a robust tactile flanker effect: responses to congruent trials were faster
 344 and more accurate than responses to incongruent trials (latency: 942 vs. 995 ms; accuracy:
 345 93.5% vs. 78.7%). Hence, we extended previous research on tactile congruency effects (Driver
 346 & Grossenbacher, 1996; Evans & Craig, 1991; Evans et al., 1992; Soto-Faraco et al., 2004),

⁴ We used a bayesian approach because it shows in a clearer manner a lack of an interaction. We include in the appendix both frequentist and bayesian analyses.

347 this time using two distractors that surrounded the target (i.e., a scenario more similar to
348 the demonstrations of the flanker effect in the visual modality). Although this effect was
349 significant for both vertical and horizontal targets, it was greater for the former, indicating
350 that the horizontal braille pattern was more difficult to detect than the vertical one. Further
351 research is needed to clarify whether those results are a product of the orientation of the
352 stimuli, or of the larger sensory field activated by the vertical stimuli (3 dots) in comparison
353 the horizontal one (2 dots).

354 We further analyzed the data to explore the temporal dynamics of the tactile flanker
355 effect, finding some similarities and differences with the standard results in the visual
356 modality. It is worth noting that given the numerous differences between tactile and visual
357 processing, as well as the differences in methodology, we cannot interpret equally the results
358 found in the present study to those found in the visual modality. However, we can compare
359 the qualitative features of results that may be modulated by modality.

360 As shown by the delta plot, the difference in RT between congruent and incongruent
361 trials increases as RT increases. Thus, tactile contextual information (irrelevant to the task)
362 influences participant's response decision more for slow responses than for fast responses.
363 Consistent with our results, delta plots in the visual modality also show an increase of the
364 congruency effect as responses get slower (e.g., Gratton et al., 1992; Hübner & Töbel, 2019).
365 From these results we cannot conclude that the tactile and visual flanker effects are
366 equivalent, since positive-going delta plots are common to many cognitive tasks (in fact, they
367 are the most common pattern of results across many manipulations). What results reveal is
368 that the time course of the flanker effect shown by delta plots in the tactile modality is not
369 qualitatively different from the one described in the visual modality. That is, the basic
370 features of delta plots do not seem sensitive to the modality differences (which does not
371 mean that there is none).

372 Interestingly, the QPF and CAF obtained from our experiment do not mimic those

373 reported in the visual modality literature. In the visual flanker task, QPFs show that error
374 responses to incongruent trials are faster than correct responses to both congruent and
375 incongruent trials (e.g., White et al., 2011), and CAFs show that for incongruent trials
376 accuracy shows an increase over time (it is very low for fast responses, increasing to nearly
377 perfect levels as responses get slower), but for congruent trials accuracy is nearly perfect
378 across all response times (Gratton et al., 1992; Hübner & Töbel, 2019; Stins et al., 2007).
379 These results suggest a greater influence of the distractors early on in the trial, in line with
380 Hypothesis_N (third row in Figure 2), and with models that explain congruency effects as a
381 result of dynamic attention (e.g., Heitz & Engle, 2007; Hübner et al., 2010). However, the
382 QPF found in our experiment shows that correct responses to congruent trials are faster
383 than both correct and error responses to incongruent trials, with not much difference
384 between the distributions of incongruent-correct and incongruent-error responses. In
385 addition, the CAFs plot shows that accuracy is higher for congruent trials than for
386 incongruent trials over time, and that the difference between does not decrease for higher RT
387 quantiles. These results indicate the influence of the distractors was constant over time, in
388 line with Hypothesis_S (second row in Figure 2), which suggests the relevant information to
389 make a decision was accumulated in a stationary manner. That is, in our tactile task,
390 attentional selectivity does not improve during the course of processing. Hence, it seems that
391 attentional control has some aspects that are specific to modality.

392 In sum, we found a tactile flanker effect that has both similarities and differences with
393 the visual flanker effect. This is taken as evidence to support that cognitive processes
394 underlying the response decision in the tactile flanker task, from the sensory input to the
395 motor response, are not totally equivalent to those in the visual flanker task. We believe
396 these results offer a start point to further research in different modalities to explore which
397 aspects of the mechanisms underlying the effect are domain-specific and which are
398 domain-general. Further research is needed to understand whether the differences between
399 visual and tactile flanker effect are caused by the specific characteristics of our perceptual

400 systems. Moreover, such investigation has real applied implications for the growing haptic
401 technology field. Technological developments that focus on a specific sensory modality can
402 be optimized using knowledge about both the modality-specific and the
403 modality-independent cognitive processes that underlie perception.

404

Open Practices

405 The online repository, available at <https://osf.io/89p3c/> , provides the bash code and
406 the stimuli lists we utilized to carry out this experiment, along with the data analyses and
407 data wrangling scripts.

408 The experiment was not pre-registered.

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Table 1

Mean accuracy, correct RTs and error RTs (in ms) per congruency condition (TRUE = congruent, FALSE = incongruent) and target type (H = horizontal, V = vertical).

Congruency	Target	Accuracy	Mean RTcorrect	Mean RTerror
FALSE	H	0.76	1061	933
FALSE	V	0.82	958	969
TRUE	H	0.92	957	895
TRUE	V	0.95	927	1021

Table 2

Likelihood ratio test results between Linear and Linear-Quadratic models

Model	AIC	BIC	logLik	deviance	Chisq	Df	Pr(>Chisq)
Linear	1,920.706	1,933.130	-956.353	1,912.706	NA	NA	NA
Linear-Quadratic	1,921.418	1,936.948	-955.709	1,911.418	1.288	1.000	0.256

Figure 1. Response time and accuracy methods used in this paper. The data to used to generate this example was simulated, following the typical figures reported in research on flanker effects in the visual modality. The code is available in the online appendix.

Figure 2. Our mapping from hypotheses to process models to data models (i.e., central tendency measures, delta plots and CAFs).

Figure 3. A diagram of a congruent trial and an incongruent trial of the tactile flanker task.

Figure 4. Mean RT (left) and accuracy (right) per target type and congruency conditions. Each soft-colored shape represent the mean of a subject in that particular condition while the means per condition across subjects are shown in hard-colored shapes.

Figure 5. Delta plot: effect over time. Each dot represents the mean RT at the .1, .3, .5, .7 and .9 quantiles.

Figure 6. Quantile probability functions: Distribution of RTs to *congruent* (black squares) and *incongruent* (white squares) trials. The two right columns are correct responses. The two left columns are error responses.

Figure 7. Conditional accuracy function: Mean accuracy for *congruent* (black squares) and *incongruent* (white squares) trials as a function of response time